

PREMIERE's 5-Step Stakeholder Engagement Strategy

Step 1: Internal Participatory Planning

The composition of this Stakeholder Engagement Strategy as part of D1.1, originally published in Open Research Europe in February 2024, was co-created and refined in an open, clear and transparent manner by PREMIERE's diverse, multi-actor consortium, consisting of partners who possess different forms of knowledge, perspectives, resources, and experiences (*practical, scientific, policy based, etc.*) over the course of preparatory meetings held via Zoom during the first 6 months of the project (*January to June 2023*), as well as during a collaborative WP1 workshop at PREMIERE's kick off meeting in Eberswalde, Germany in March 2023.

Step 2: AKIS Stakeholder Identification & Mapping

The resultant co-creation of an internal database of AKIS Stakeholders, balanced across the Quadruple Helix Model (QHM) of Innovation (*Government/Policy; Science/Academia; Industry/Business & Society/Community*), at European, national and regional Level (*via NUTS Regions*) in each of the 27 EU Member States, who participate (or intend to participate) in the planning, preparation and drafting of multi-actor Horizon Europe project proposals, and related policy instruments, is actively being populated & periodically updated by the entire PREMIERE consortium.

Step 3: AKIS Stakeholder Categorisation & Analysis

Stage 1: Co-Creation of PREMIERE's 7 Stakeholder Profile Types

PREMIERE's pan-European database of AKIS Stakeholders mapped across the QHM was subsequently analysed and categorised into 7 Stakeholder Types following a profiling exercise carried out by the consortium at PREMIERE's GA in Ghent, Belgium in Feb 2024 as part of D1.3 in order to help guide participant recruitment efforts for the project's 5 WPs in the next step of the strategy (Step 4) as well as to determine the most appropriate communication tools required to engage with the different types of AKIS stakeholders.

Stage 2: Stakeholder Interest/Influence Matrix at Work Package (WP) Level

PREMIERE's WP Leaders will be invited to break down the 7 Stakeholder Profile Types categorised in Stage 1 into two main characteristics based on their perceived level of interest in the tasks & results of their respective WPs, as well as the 7 typologies' ability to influence the actions & outcomes of these WPs to help orientate WP specific C,D&E efforts in Step 4 and Step 5.

Step 4: AKIS Stakeholder Engagement & Co-Creation

The knowledge garnered from the initial three stages of the Stakeholder Engagement Strategy, enables partners to select and recruit a representative sample of actors within the AKIS ecosystem from across policy, research and practice, particularly harder to reach groups, to participate in the project's 5 interrelated WPs in a systematic and unbiased manner, & also to decide on an appropriate course of action (e.g. tailored tools) to involve selected actors in the various engagement efforts, activities & tasks of their WPs in a co-creative & inclusive way, thereby helping to ensure that project outputs reflect the needs & expectations of 'end-users'.

Step 5: Dissemination and Exploitation (D&E)

PREMIERE's D&E plan (D1.4) defines how the project will conduct the implementation of all dissemination and exploitation activities resulting from the outcomes and outputs of the five interrelated WPs of PREMIERE, to each of the 7 Stakeholder Profile Types identified in Step 3, as well as the wider public at European, national and regional level, through the utilisation of appropriate channels and tools in clear and unambiguous language.